

Prevention of Oxidative Stress in HEK293 Cells by Vitamins D, B9, and E

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Abstract

Various studies (1,2) in the literature have repeatedly demonstrated the antioxidant effects of vitamins. However, most of these studies have evaluated their effects in isolation (3) and ignored their combined influence. In this research, the prevention of hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress in the HEK293 (Human Embryonic Kidney) cell line by combinations of vitamins B9, D, and E — not previously studied together in this cell line — was investigated. Different concentrations and combinations of these vitamins [Vitamin D (10/50/100 μM)], [Vitamin E (25/50/100 μM)], [Vitamin B9 (50/100/200 μM)] were applied to the cells along with 10 μL of 200 μM hydrogen peroxide. Metabolic activity was measured using the MTT assay, and a migration (scratch) test was performed. Among the cells exposed to oxidative stress, the highest metabolic activity was observed in the group containing B9 (50 μM). Among the combinations, the highest metabolic activity was recorded in the group containing both E (25 μM) and B9 (50 μM). Based on these findings, further research could be conducted on pharmaceuticals combining vitamins E and B9.

Keywords: Oxidative stress, vitamin, antioxidant

Introduction

In recent years, the importance of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Multiple Sclerosis has become increasingly recognized. Although the exact causes of these diseases remain unclear, oxidative stress is known to contribute to many health issues, including cancer formation and neurodegeneration. Current treatment methods for these conditions are often insufficient. Therefore, vitamins E, B9, and D — known for their natural antioxidant properties — are proposed as potential protective agents. Although the antioxidant activities of vitamins E(4), B9(5), and D(6) have been reported, their mechanisms and efficiencies are not fully understood and remain under investigation. Previous studies have explored the combined antioxidant effects of vitamins E and D in mice(7); however, human cell studies remain limited. HEK293 cells express genes active in vitamin D metabolism(8), and similar behavior has been observed for vitamin B9(9), whereas vitamin E metabolism is relatively low in kidney cells(10). Therefore, by comparing the antioxidant effects of these vitamins — two of which are more active (B9 and D) and one less active (E) — the study aims to identify which combinations may be most optimal in treating or preventing oxidative stress-related diseases such as Alzheimer's or cancer. Based on previous findings, it is hypothesized that the combination of these three vitamins will effectively reduce oxidative stress.

Materials and Methods

Cell Culture:

HEK293 cells were obtained and transferred into a cell culture flask (Figure 4.1). They were incubated at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ environment using DMEM (Dulbecco’s Modified Eagle Medium, high glucose) supplemented with 10% FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum) and Pen-Strep antibiotics until they reached sufficient confluence. The cells were then transferred into 96-well and 6-well plates for the planned assays (Figures 4.2 and 4.3). After incubation with EDTA-containing trypsin for five minutes, the cells were detached, centrifuged, the supernatant was removed, and fresh medium was added to ensure homogenous distribution.

Condition	IC50 Value (µL)
E Vitamin Standalone	69.00360153114157
B9 Vitamin Standalone	39.629990295103724
B9 Vitamin + H2O2 Combination	Fit failed
D + E + B9 Standalone	54.31102550628783
D + E + B9 + H2O2 Combination	55.11626804746094
D Vitamin Standalone	7.587735885727925
D + H2O2 Combination	8.447345905143132

Table 1 and 2: dose–response estimates. Every vitamin and hydrogen peroxidised were added by 10 µL. The amount of hydrogen peroxide used is 200 µM.

After reaching the desired density, cells in 96-well plates were treated with vitamin solutions at different concentrations. To induce oxidative stress, hydrogen peroxide — a strong reactive oxygen species(11) — was added to designated groups. Cells were incubated for 12 hours.

	A	B	C	D
1	D 10 μ M	E 25 μ M	B9 50 μ M	D 10 μ M + E 25 μ M
2	D 50 μ M	E 50 μ M	B9 100 μ M	D 10 μ M + B9 50 μ M
3	D 100 μ M	E 100 μ M	B9 200 μ M	E 25 μ M + B9 50 μ M
4	D 10 μ M + H2O2	E 25 μ M + H2O2	B9 50 μ M + H2O2	D 10 μ M + E 25 μ M + H2O2
5	D 50 μ M + H2O2	E 50 μ M + H2O2	B9 100 μ M + H2O2	D 10 μ M + B9 50 μ M + H2O2
6	D 100 μ M + H2O2	E 100 μ M + H2O2	B9 200 μ M + H2O2	E 25 μ M + B9 50 μ M + H2O2
7	DMEM	DMEM	DMEM	DMEM
8	H2O2	H2O2	H2O2	H2O2

Table 3: Seeding of Cells in Plates

For the MTT assay, required solutions were prepared: the MTT reagent was dissolved in buffer, and formazan crystals were later dissolved using SDS-containing solvent. Following treatment, absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm to determine metabolic activity(12).

Scratch assays were also performed on 6-well plates to assess migration at 0, 12, and 24 hours post-scratch.

Results

After 12 hours, metabolic activity was analyzed via MTT assay. The results are shown below.

	1	2	3	4
A	1,397	0,577	1,227	0,415
B	1,146	0,665	3,608	0,671
C	0,999	0,916	3,741	0,909
D	1,434	0,567	1,381	0,51
E	1,272	1,541	3,751	0,719
F	0,986	0,841	3,687	0,856
G	0,424	1,024	0,402	0,492
H	0,735	0,64	1,035	0,621

Table 4: MTT Assay Results (12th Hour Readings)

Migration assays were analyzed and photographed at 0, 12, and 24 hours. Figures 1-3 below are the microscope viewings of those Assays.

Figure 1:Migration Assay under microscope at hour 0

Figure 2: Migration Assay under microscope at hour 12

Figure 3: Migration Assay under microscope at hour 24

Conclusion and Discussion

Among the tested groups, the combination of vitamins B9 (50 μ M) and E (25 μ M) provided the greatest protection against oxidative stress while showing the least cytotoxicity. Vitamin B9 alone also exhibited minimal cytotoxic effects. Vitamins D and B9, when used together, showed more optimal protection than when applied separately. All combinations effectively mitigated oxidative stress.

The combination of E and B9 was also most effective in the migration test, with complete wound closure observed within 24 hours. This suggests that at the tested concentrations, the combination demonstrated low cytotoxicity and strong antioxidative protection. Overall, these vitamin combinations may serve as low-toxicity therapeutic candidates for preventing and treating oxidative stress-related diseases.

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